

A Qualitative Exploration of the MATATAG Curriculum's Perceived Impact on History and Geography Education in the School Year 2024-2025

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Abstract:

This study presents a qualitative examination of the influence of the MATATAG curriculum on history and geography education for the academic year 2024-2025. Through the utilization of Focused Group Discussions (FGD) and interviews involving stakeholders in social studies education, a systematic collection, analysis, and interpretation of participant responses were conducted. FGD outcomes uncovered diverse themes regarding the perceived impact of the MATATAG curriculum on the teaching of history and geography. These themes encompass heightened awareness of contemporary and critical issues, deepened understanding with expanded perspectives, varied

outcomes based on implementation, early exposure to history and geography, addressing knowledge gaps and fostering patriotism, impact on discipline and awareness, intensified focus on geography and history, and the teacher's perspective and meaningful learning. The results highlight substantial positive changes attributed to the MATATAG curriculum compared to its predecessor, as outlined in the curriculum guides issued by the Department of Education. Noteworthy is the curriculum's provision of opportunities for the localization and contextualization of history and geography lessons. This paper contributes novel insights into the perceptions of diverse stakeholders regarding the imminent implementation of the MATATAG curriculum in the upcoming school year.

Keywords: *History Education, Geography Education, MATATAG Curriculum, Qualitative Exploration, Social Studies.*

Introduction

The curriculum encompasses the meticulously planned and organized courses, activities, and experiences learners partake in throughout their educational journey. It stands as a cornerstone within education systems, wielding profound influence over what learners learn and how they acquire knowledge. Curriculum is a planned learning experiences of a school or educational institution, encompassing what is planned for students, what is delivered to them, and what

they experience (Oliveira, 2008). The curriculum is not neutral, but rather a vehicle of selected knowledge that is binding to power and can homogenize or differentiate school (Roberts, 2015). It is underpinned by a set of values and beliefs about what students should know and how they come to know (Morris, 1955). The curriculum is the primary concern of all participants in the educative enterprise, as it is the main object of lay concern and criticisms (Thaib & Siswanto, 2015). Effective curriculum

management is crucial for achieving educational goals and improving learning outcomes.

The significance of curriculum resides in its capacity to align with society's evolving needs and objectives, equipping learners to navigate the complexities of the future and ensuring that education resonates with real-world applications. A relevant curriculum not only adapts to the dynamic requirements of learners, educators, and the job market but also considers the contextual nuances of the contemporary world (Sivesind, 2023). Making curriculum content relevant is important so that learners can apply what they have learned from school to real-life situations (Gomez et al., 2020). Furthermore, it is recognized as a pivotal force in shaping the destinies of learners, playing a pivotal role in citizen training, and fostering the development of values and skills (Mapolisa et al., 2017). The absence of curriculum reform as an institutional framework poses a tangible risk to public education systems with democratic functions, potentially leading to unforeseen consequences for society (Gomez et al., 2020).

The Philippine education system is poised for a transformative shift, aiming to align its basic education standards with global benchmarks. This pivotal change will be realized through meticulous attention to curriculum development, ensuring its appropriateness, responsiveness, and relevance to learners nationally and globally (Department of Education, 2019; Department of Education, 2023a). MATATAG is the term used for the new curriculum in the Philippines, as outlined in the General Shaping Paper published by the Department of Education (2023a).

The MATATAG curriculum has undergone noteworthy changes, including a reduction in the number of competencies to address overcrowding issues in the curriculum. Additionally, the Good Manners and Right Conduct (GMRC) and Values Education have been integrated and intensified, aligning with legal requirements. Another significant shift is the heightened emphasis on social studies, a crucial element in realizing the Department of

Education's vision of nurturing Filipinos with a deep and passionate love for the country.

In the upcoming School Year 2024-2025, the inaugural phase of the MATATAG curriculum will be rolled out. Consequently, it is crucial to delve into diverse perspectives to anticipate and understand the potential impacts of the curriculum on teaching social studies courses, such as history and geography. This paper endeavors to gather insights from a group of participants to unveil their views and perspectives on the potential impact of the MATATAG curriculum on the study of history and geography.

Research Questions

In general, this paper sought to explore the MATATAG curriculum's impact on History and Geography Education. Specifically, it aimed to address the following:

1. What is the perceived potential impact of the MATATAG Curriculum on the study of History and Geography at the basic education level, commencing in the school year 2024-2025?
2. Does the MATATAG Curriculum represent an enhancement compared to the current curriculum in terms of how History and Geography are taught?
3. Explore the opportunities for localizing and contextualizing History and Geography lessons within the framework of the MATATAG curriculum.

Materials and Methods

This paper employed a qualitative research methodology, utilizing Focus Group Discussion (FGD) as the primary approach. The participants deliberately selected for relevance include six (6) social studies teachers from the Department of Education at both elementary and high school levels, two (2) grade level coordinators, and six (6) teacher education students and six (6) instructors from higher education institutions. The researcher extended invitations to these participants, facilitating a substantive discussion through the Zoom

meeting platform and face-to-face interactions to delve into the nuances of the MATATAG curriculum. In addition to the FGD, the researcher conducted interviews with colleagues specializing in social studies teaching. These interviews aimed to capture supplementary insights regarding their perspectives on the MATATAG curriculum and its potential impact on the instruction of history and geography within basic education.

Results

The Perceived Potential Impact of the MATATAG Curriculum on the Study of History and Geography at the Basic Education Level

The Focused Group Discussions and the interviews draw the following significant themes from the analysis of the conversations and engagement. Themes drawn from the responses of the participants on the potential impact of the MATATAG curriculum include increasing awareness of contemporary and critical issues, deepening understanding and broadening perspectives, varied results based on implementation, early exposure to history and geography, addressing knowledge gaps and promoting love for country, impact on discipline and awareness, intensified focus on geography and history, and teacher perspective and meaningful learning.

Increasing Awareness of Contemporary and Critical Issues

The forthcoming implementation of the MATATAG Curriculum is poised to exert a profound influence on learners, with expectations running high for heightened awareness of contemporary and critical issues, including sensitive topics such as extrajudicial killings (EJK). This intentional focus on pressing societal matters is a commendable step towards fostering a socially aware and engaged generation.

However, amid these positive expectations, legitimate concerns have surfaced, particularly regarding the potential for historical distortion

within the curriculum. Some voices express apprehension about an imbalance in the treatment of historical themes, emphasizing overarching concepts like dictatorship without providing comprehensive discussions of specific historical events. This concern underscores the importance of striking a delicate balance between addressing broad historical themes and delving into the nuanced details of significant events. This ensures that learners receive a well-rounded and accurate understanding of historical contexts.

In navigating these considerations, it becomes crucial for educators, curriculum developers, and stakeholders to collaboratively address the concerns raised, seeking an equilibrium that not only enhances awareness of contemporary issues but also upholds the integrity and accuracy of historical narratives. This balance ensures that learners emerge from their educational journey not only socially conscious but also equipped with a nuanced and accurate understanding of the historical events that have shaped their society.

Deepening Understanding and Broadening Perspectives

Participants in the discourse surrounding the MATATAG Curriculum eagerly anticipate its potential to elevate the understanding of the significance of historical events in both the Philippines and the global context. There is a collective aspiration for the curriculum to act as a catalyst for a more profound comprehension, allowing learners to delve into the intricacies of pivotal moments that have shaped the nation and the broader world. The aim is not just to impart factual information but to instill a sense of historical consciousness that goes beyond rote memorization, fostering critical thinking and a deeper appreciation for the complexities inherent in historical narratives.

In addition to historical enrichment, participants underscored the importance of the curriculum in broadening learners' knowledge and awareness of contemporary social concerns. By integrating these issues into the educational framework, the curriculum aims to cultivate socially responsible citizens who are well-versed in the challenges

and opportunities that characterize the present era. The emphasis on fostering analytical thinking and geographic comprehension is viewed as an investment in equipping learners with the tools to navigate an interconnected world. The hope is that this expanded perspective will contribute to academic excellence and lay a robust foundation for learners' future roles as informed, engaged, and meaningful contributors to society.

Varied Results Based on Implementation

As articulated by a student-teacher participant, the anticipated impact of the new curriculum on the study of history and geography is perceived as contingent on several critical factors, including the curriculum's structural design, the richness of its content, and the efficacy of the employed teaching methods. This insightful perspective underscores the need for a nuanced evaluation beyond a surface-level examination. The participant emphasizes the importance of scrutinizing whether the curriculum effectively aligns with the primary objectives of education, particularly in fostering not just the accumulation of knowledge but a deep understanding of historical and geographical contexts. The emphasis on encouraging critical thinking serves as a cornerstone in this assessment, reflecting a broader commitment to cultivating analytical skills that empower learners to engage with historical and geographic concepts in a meaningful and thought-provoking manner.

Early Exposure to History and Geography

The recently introduced curriculum presents a valuable opportunity for young learners to delve into history and geography from an early age, setting the stage for a well-rounded educational foundation. This intentional exposure aims to cultivate a heightened awareness of global events, fostering a sense of connectedness and curiosity about the world. The underlying philosophy is that by introducing historical and geographical concepts early, learners can develop a solid framework for comprehending the unfolding complexities of contemporary global affairs. The curriculum's emphasis on linking current events with historical context is

designed to empower learners with a more profound and nuanced understanding, equipping them with the tools to navigate an increasingly interconnected world with insight and discernment. Early exposure to history and geography is envisioned not only as an educational venture but as a catalyst for nurturing informed, engaged, and globally aware citizens from the outset of their academic journey.

Addressing Knowledge Gaps and Promoting Love for History

Recognizing the necessity of studying history at the basic education level, participants highlight the need to address knowledge gaps, especially concerning Filipino history. Concerns are expressed about learners needing to become more familiar with foreign pop culture than their history. Studying history and geography at the basic education level is an essential step, serving as an eye-opener for learners to love history and actively seek information about it.

Impact on Discipline and Awareness

Acknowledging the potential positive impact on discipline and awareness, participants note the curriculum's role in countering negative trends observed through social media. Education is seen as a means to expand knowledge and rekindle awareness of Filipino culture, contributing to a more disciplined and culturally aware student body.

Intensified Focus on Geography's Role in History

The curriculum's increased focus on geography is receiving widespread acclaim for its positive impact on understanding the country's history. People are particularly pleased with incorporating crucial topics such as the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS), recognizing its relevance in addressing contemporary maritime issues and their broader implications. Furthermore, the expanded attention to a more detailed exploration of Southeast Asia is seen as a valuable enhancement, offering learners a deeper insight into the historical, cultural, and geopolitical dynamics within this significant

region. This deliberate expansion of geographical content is perceived as academically beneficial and as a means of fostering a broader perspective among learners, cultivating their awareness of the interconnected nature of historical and geographical factors both on a national and global scale. In essence, the curriculum's dedication to a comprehensive exploration of geography is earning commendation for its potential to nurture a more informed and globally aware citizenry.

Teacher Perspective and Meaningful Learning

From a teacher's perspective, there is satisfaction with the curriculum's focus on geography and history. The curriculum will likely result in meaningful learning rather than rote memorization, fostering a more intense appreciation and awareness of history and geography among learners. The overarching sentiment is that the MATATAG Curriculum holds the potential to shape informed and culturally aware individuals, contributing to the development of responsible and patriotic citizens.

Comparative Analysis between MATATAG Curriculum and Present Curriculum in terms of teaching History and Geography

Following the Focused Group Discussion (FGD), a unanimous agreement emerged among participants regarding the MATATAG curriculum's role in introducing diverse enhancements to elevate the quality of teaching History and Geography within the basic education level. Analysis of participant responses underscores their optimism for meaningful reforms within the education sector resulting from this development.

Upon a thorough examination of both the old and new curriculum guides (Department of Education, 2016, 2023b), discernible shifts between the two become apparent. For instance, although the core course descriptions remain consistent in the teaching of "*Ang Bansang Pilipinas*," the new curriculum exhibits noteworthy improvements. Notably, it facilitates a smoother transition in discussions. It

introduces topics such as the historical basis of geography, the constitution as its basis, the executive orders released relating to it, and the Archipelagic Doctrines such as the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS). This holds significant implications for teaching history and geography, particularly given the contemporary international disputes in the West Philippine Sea. Enhanced awareness of these topics empowers learners to analyze historical and geographical details critically.

Furthermore, the updated curriculum emphasizes discussing natural resources and their implications for economic development. Proficiency in geography becomes pivotal in executing this effectively, given its direct connection to exploring environmental concerns and issues. Lastly, the inclusion of intensified discussions on peace education and civics enhances the overall quality of teaching history and geography at the basic education level.

In summary, the MATATAG curriculum constitutes a substantial leap forward, ushering in significant improvements in the study of history and geography.

The Opportunity for Localizing and Contextualizing History and Geography Lessons within the Framework of the MATATAG Curriculum

The MATATAG curriculum empowers learners, fostering competence, knowledge, and productivity. It achieves this by seamlessly integrating diverse content to enhance foundational skills and promote metacognition for lifelong learning. The curriculum provides opportunities for localizing and contextualizing history and geography lessons and employs a range of teaching strategies and techniques. These approaches not only adhere to the Department's guidelines but are also tailored to meet the specific needs of learners, aligning with performance standards for a comprehensive educational experience. By scrutinizing the available documents encompassing the study of history and geography, performance standards play a pivotal role in advocating for the localization and contextualization of lessons. This approach empowers learners by providing

them with the suitable environment, tools, and input essential for their holistic development.

Conclusion

This paper undertook a qualitative exploration of the impact of the MATATAG curriculum on history and geography education for the school year 2024-2025. Employing Focused Group Discussions (FGD) and interviews with individuals vested in social studies education, I systematically collected, analyzed, and interpreted participant responses. The FGD results revealed several themes concerning the perceived impact of the MATATAG curriculum on the study of history and geography, including heightened awareness of contemporary and critical issues, deepened understanding with expanded perspectives, varied outcomes based on implementation, early exposure to history and geography, addressing knowledge gaps and fostering patriotism, impact on discipline and awareness, intensified focus on geography and history, and the teacher's perspective and meaningful learning.

The findings indicate significant positive changes, evident in the MATATAG curriculum compared to its predecessor, as elucidated in the curriculum guides published by the Department of Education. Notably, the MATATAG curriculum offers opportunities for the localization and contextualization of history and geography lessons. This paper contributes fresh insights into how various stakeholders perceive the forthcoming implementation of the MATATAG curriculum in the upcoming school year.

Conflict of Interests

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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